

FFP regulations effects on financial results and on audit opinion.

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Research question and objective

The auditor has to express their opinion in the audit report. This opinion reflects whether the financial statements presented by the companies meet the legally required criteria and fully represent the reality of the firm. The Union of European Football Associations (UEFA), the governing body of European football, concerned about the financial health of clubs, approved in 2010 the Financial Fair Play (FFP) Regulation. Since 2011, all football clubs that want to participate in UEFA competitions must comply with it. Subsequently, in 2012 and 2015 FFP was updated. This regulation, in order to verify the financial viability of the teams, established that clubs must present their annual financial statements audited by an independent external auditor for obtaining the license that allows to take part in UEFA competitions. UEFA will evaluate the content of the auditor's report and may deny the license in three cases. First, the auditor denies or presents an adverse opinion. Second, when the audit report contains qualifications or a paragraph of emphasis on going concern. Third, if the audit report includes qualification paragraphs on matters other than going concern about the operating accounting principle or paragraphs of emphasis, and these are significant for the presentation of the faithful image of the financial and patrimonial situation and results of the applicant club. If clubs fail to comply with the criteria set out in these regulations may lead to sanctions and may be denied the license to participate in UEFA competitions. This fact could lead to serious damages to the sanctioned club, as competitions such as the Champions League or Europa League provide significant revenue to clubs. This could jeopardize their financial viability (Dimitropoulos, 2016).

In addition, this regulation pays special attention to compliance with the club's ability to continue as a functioning company. This can be due to the delicate financial situation shown by some of the European football clubs, marked by their growing debts and persistent deficits (García & Rodríguez, 2003, Barajas, 2004, Ascari & Gagnepain, 2006, Boscá, Liern, Martínez & Sala, 2008, Gay, 2009a, 2009b, Barajas & Rodríguez, 2010, Gammelsaeter, 2010, Storm & Nielsen, 2012, Deloitte, 2014; Robinson & Simmons, 2014). European football presents serious financial problems, the result of imbalances between income and expenditure, therefore, increase in debt. This has led some clubs to operate on the verge of bankruptcy, with a significant number in bankruptcy administration. Kuper & Szymanski (2009) observed that between 1992 and 2008 forty English professional clubs have been involved in insolvency proceedings, and Beech, Horsman & Magraw (2010) declare that among the first and second division members of the English Football League for the 2008-09 season, more than half had suffered an insolvency event in recent years. In Spain, at the end of 2011, 22 clubs were or had been in administration (Barajas & Rodríguez, 2014).

Therefore, with the approval of the Financial Fair Play Regulation, the auditors have an important role in order to verify the financial information of the teams related to their responsibility in the issuance of the audit opinion. In this sense, the independence when

issuing the opinion on the financial statements will be key. The auditors could be pressured by the management of clubs to obtain reports with clean opinions, in order to meet the requirements imposed by the regulation of the Financial Fair Play and ensure the license to participate in UEFA competitions. Ruiz-Barbadillo (2016) states that the meaning that users associate with the receipt of a non-clean report may involve a cost for the company and specifically for its managers, since the auditor when issuing an unfavorable opinion is questioning the quality of the information audited. This fact can lead managers to try to intimidate or pressure the auditor to issue a report with favorable opinion, creating a threat to the auditor on the level of independence with which he has to act. This way of proceeding may damage the interests of the shareholders (members), since it diminishes the quality of the audit and the reliability of the audited accounting information, besides being a fraud, and that could affect the decisions that are going to take the different users of this information (De Angelo, 1982, Archambeault & DeZoort, 2001, Ruiz-Barbadillo & Gómez-Aguilar, 2007).

The previous literature on the improvement of audit opinion, regardless of the circumstance that provokes it, has focused on the phenomenon known as "opinion shopping". Ruiz-Barbadillo & Gómez-Aguilar (2007) denote that it is a phenomenon that is based on changing the audit firm by hiring a new auditor who accepts certain accounting practices with the objective that the audited company can get an improvement of opinion, although such practices entail a lower reliability of the accounting information to disclose. These authors point out that a simple definition of this concept is given by Krishnan & Stephens (1995), "search for a better audit opinion through the realization of a change of auditor". In this sense, previous studies, both nationally and internationally have tried to obtain evidence of the possible relationship between the reception of an unfavorable report and the auditor change, which is not conclusive. There are a good number of studies that do find a relationship between both variables such as those published by Bedingfiel & Loeb (1974), Chow & Rice (1982), Craswell (1988), Roberts et al. (1990), Sarhan et al. (1991), Citron & Taffler (1992), Beattie & Fearnley (1995), Krishnan et al. (1996), García-Benau et al. (2000), Ruiz-Barbadillo & Gómez-Aguilar (2003) or Sánchez-Segura (2003). On the contrary, works such as Burton & Roberts (1967), De Angelo (1982), Schwartz & Menon (1985), Smith (1986), Willians (1988), Haskins & Willians (1990), Krishnan (1994) or Gómez -Aguilar & Ruiz-Barbadillo (2000) find no association between receiving an unfavorable opinion and the change of auditor. The existence of a change of auditor will not always imply an improvement of opinion after the change, and there is evidence in both directions.

It is in this context, the objective of this investigation is to see if after the approval of the Financial Fair Play Regulation, there is an improvement of the opinion issued in the audit report. This could be expected as this regulation denotes that when the opinion of the report is not favorable, UEFA can deny the license to the clubs for taking part in the European competitions. As far as we know there is no study that has addressed the possible improvement of opinion for the football industry, and this has been what motivated this research. In addition, it is studied if in the case that there was an improvement of opinion, this was related to a change of the auditor. Previously, a descriptive analysis on the evolution of finances of clubs is introduced.

Data and methodology

The analysis will be carried out for the football teams of the Spanish First Division (currently Liga Santander). The information included in the annual accounts and their corresponding audit reports have been used. This information has been obtained through

various sources, websites of the football teams, the Spanish Professional Football League and the Companies House where the teams have the obligation of deposit their accounts. Therefore, the initial sample should consist of the data of 20 football teams with a follow-up of eleven years, for each of the seasons between the 2007/08 and 2017/18 years. Only the first division teams have been taken into account as they have the option to participate in UEFA competitions (Champions League and Europa League).

There are two hypotheses:

H1: The probability of receiving an audit report with a modified opinion or going concern modified opinion after the approval of the Financial Fair Play regulation decreases.

H2: The probability of receiving an audit report with a modified opinion or going concern modified opinion after the approval of the Financial Fair Play regulation decreases if there is also a change in the audit firm.

Two models using Probit and Logit Regression with panel data analysis are used:

$OPINION = f (REGULATION, AUDITFIRM_CHANGE, AUDITOR, LOSS, ROA, LEV, SIZE)$

$OPINION = f (REGULATION, REGULATION * AUDITFIRM_CHANGE, AUDITFIRM_CHANGE, AUDITOR, LOSS, ROA, LEV, SIZE)$.

Variables	Definition	Sign
<i>Dependent Variable</i>		
OPINION	1 the auditor issues an audit report with modified opinion (qualified opinion, disclaimer opinion and adverse opinion) or with a going concern modified opinion; 0 otherwise.	
<i>Variable of interest</i>		
REGUL	1 years after Financial Fair Play Rules (ejercicios 2010/11 hasta el 2015/16); 0 otherwise. (we can use also PRE- TRANS- and POST-)	-
<i>Control variables</i>		
AUDITFIRM_CHANG	1 if there were a change in the audit firm; 0 otherwise.	-
AUDITOR	1 if auditor is one of the Big4 (Deloitte , PriceWaterhouseCoopers (PWC) , Ernst & Young (EY) y KPMG); 0 otherwise.	+
LOSS	1 if there were losses in the previous year; 0 otherwise	+
ROA	EBIT/AT	-
LEV	Debt/AT	+
SIZE	Log AT	-

Descriptive Statistics

OPINION	Pre-FFP	Trans-FFP	FFP
Clean	21.1%	29.3%	65.3%
Qualified	79.0%	70.7%	34.7%

Ongoing concern	Pre-FFP	Trans-FFP	FFP
No	43.9%	39.7%	72.2%
Yes	56.1%	60.3%	27.8%

Graph 1. Comparison of Net Profit before and after FFP

VARIABLES	(Probit) Unqualified	(Logit) Unqualified
Pre-FFP	0.765*** (0.291)	1.312** (0.519)
Loss t-1	1.282*** (0.293)	2.230*** (0.529)
big4	-1.931*** (0.436)	-3.452*** (0.812)
Change	0.200 (0.408)	0.562 (0.761)
lta	0.402*** (0.147)	0.706*** (0.264)
roa	-2.497*** (0.908)	-4.322*** (1.649)
lev	2.196*** (0.550)	4.293*** (1.122)
Constant	-9.537*** (2.782)	-17.12*** (5.019)
Observations	213	213
Pseudo R2	0.530	0.534

Standard errors in parentheses
 *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

